

Trends in overall extinction risk for indigenous taxa in Aotearoa New Zealand

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Abstract

The distinctive biogeography of the archipelago of Aotearoa New Zealand, its levels of endemism and many taxa with restricted ranges demand conservation metrics tailored to the national context. We computed the first New Zealand national Red List Index (NZ national RLI) using the New Zealand Threat Classification System (NZTCS). This preprint describes the methodology and succinct results to this study, which is currently in preparation for publication. Incorporating the conservation status of 9,297 taxa (approximately 25% of the country's identified biota) between 2005-2025 using a context relevant to New Zealand, the index's value lies in its ability to track genuine changes in conservation status and associated overall extinction risk over time, and to highlight knowledge gaps (particularly fungi, and within the invertebrates). Although the NZ national RLI shows a stable trend over the last two decades, this does not imply that biodiversity loss in Aotearoa has halted, as its aggregated nature conceals individual taxa still suffering population declines within or across conservation status categories and 5-yearly assessments do not capture rapid changes. The RLI should be interpreted alongside other indicators (e.g. population abundance, habitat extent and condition, and threat intensity). Future work should continue to expand taxonomic coverage of the NZTCS and explore disaggregation at ecologically meaningful scales, which may enable this tool to inform adaptive management and accelerate progress toward halting biodiversity loss.

Keywords: biodiversity, biota, conservation status, New Zealand Threat Classification System, NZTCS, Red List Index, taxonomic groups, threatened species

1. Introduction

Changes in the conservation status of taxa are often used as indicators of trends in national and global biodiversity. However, changes in conservation status over time do not necessarily reflect a genuine change in species actual status, as they are often the result of improved knowledge on species distribution and biology, revised criteria or revised taxonomy. To address this, the International Union for the Conservation of Nature (IUCN) developed the Red List Index (RLI) based on genuine status change from the IUCN Red List assessments. This index measures genuine conservation status changes over time, and is used by government and NGOs to track progress towards achieving Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) targets, as defined under the international Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD, Butchart et al. 2025). The IUCN provide an aggregated global RLI (www.iucnredlist.org/assessment/red-list-index) for five taxonomic groups (those in which all species have been assessed at least twice): birds, mammals, amphibians, cycads and warm-water reef-forming corals. A disaggregated global RLI is also provided for 253 individual countries based on the methodology of Butchart et al. (2010).

While disaggregated global RLIs track the contribution of nations toward global trends in extinction risk (Butchart et al. 2025), they can poorly reflect conservation progress at the national level (Raimondo et al. 2023). Disaggregated global RLIs are based on species' global distributions and include only five major taxonomic groups (birds, mammals, amphibians, cycads, and corals), which limits their representativeness for nations with diverse

and unique biota. For example, for Aotearoa New Zealand (here after Aotearoa), this index could only be based on the global distribution of 48 species of mammals, 233 species of birds, 4 species of amphibians and 13 species of corals over a period ranging from 1993-2020. To address this gap, Raimondo et al (2023) presented a complementary approach that assesses genuine changes in national extinction risk for the proportion of species' populations occurring within a country's boundaries. These national RLIs can be computed from a greater diversity of taxonomic groups and therefore better reflect a nation's effectiveness in reducing extinction risk for the populations of species for which it is accountable. The calculation of a national RLI is a valuable addition to national biodiversity state and trend benchmarking and can guide conservation actions and protective legislation for threatened species (Szabo et al. 2010). Because national RLIs are calculated based on different taxonomic groups and methodologies, these indices are not suitable for comparing progress across countries, nor for tracking global goals and targets (Raimondo et al. 2023). Global and national RLIs are therefore complementary, and countries are strongly encouraged to report on both (Butchart et al. 2025).

The limited scope and representativeness of global RLIs is particularly problematic for countries with distinctive ecological contexts. Aotearoa, island biogeography has shaped a unique and highly endemic biodiversity, making a tailored national approach to conservation assessment essential. The New Zealand Threat Classification System (NZTCS) was developed to complement the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Red List of Threatened Species which provides a health indicator for the world biodiversity and is used globally to inform policy and conservation decisions. The NZTCS criteria and categories were defined to take into consideration the country's insular system, great diversity of ecosystems, large number of taxa with naturally restricted ranges and / or small population sizes and the period over which recent declines have occurred (de Lange and Norton 1998; Molloy et al. 2002; Townsend et al. 2008). The NZTCS has been used since 2002 to assess the conservation status of Aotearoa indigenous taxa and guide national priorities. Assessing the risk of extinction of taxa at the level of a nation is critical to inform and implement national conservation policies and to report on national targets defined by international conventions (e.g. CBD) (IUCN 2012, IUCN 2024, Raymondo et al. 2023).

In comparison to RLIs calculated from global assessments, the NZTCS dataset allows the inclusion of a wider array of taxonomic groups, including less studied groups such as invertebrates and non-vascular plants, across the broader environment: terrestrial, marine and freshwater. Aotearoa indigenous vascular plant taxa, for example, were first assessed in 2001, when 995 taxa were listed and were re-assessed consecutively in 2005, 2008, 2012, 2017, with the latest assessment of 2,844 taxa occurring in 2023 (Hitchmough 2002, Hitchmough et al. 2007, de Lange et al. 2009, 2013, 2018, 2024, respectively). In this study, we assessed genuine change in the conservation status of Aotearoa taxa over time following the IUCN Red List index (RLI) methodology. We computed RLIs based on the number of taxa in each NZTCS category and the number that changed categories between assessments, because of genuine improvement or deterioration in status. We derived the first national aggregated RLI for Aotearoa that is representative of the country's unique biogeography. Based on national-scale assessments of extinction risk, the New Zealand national RLI index provides a metric of biodiversity trend that can highlight national biodiversity improvements and losses.

2. Methods

New Zealand Threat Classification System (NZTCS)

The NZTCS criteria and categories include 14 conservation statuses, ensuring that all possible combinations of status and trend are covered within the different categories (de Lange and Norton 1998, Molloy et al. 2001, Rolfe et al. 2022). The NZTCS lists taxa to the lowest taxonomic level at which they have been formally described, and uses informal tag names, unofficial, "working" names given to putative new taxa that have not yet been formally described and named according to scientific nomenclature (Molloy et al. 2002). These informal tag names act as temporary placeholders for putative taxa to help with consistent identification and conservation efforts, especially when a population has a small size or occupies a threatened habitat (Leschen et al. 2009, Heenan and Rogers 2019). The NZTCS provides a more sensitive classification of the Aotearoa biota which has been shaped by the country's isolated and mountainous geography. The conservation status of groups of taxa (e.g. birds, reptiles, vascular plants) is assessed by panels of experts, using the NZTCS, approximately every 5 years; and resulting data are made publicly available on the NZTCS database (nztcs.org.nz). As per 2025, the NZTCS provides more than 20 years of data for over 15,000 taxa, most of which have been re-assessed at least twice. The total number of taxa assessed for their conservation status using the NZTCS almost tripled from 5,442 in 2005 to 15,374 in 2025.

Genuine changes in conservation status

To allow visualisation of genuine changes in conservation status over time, for each species, we determined the 'NZTCS adjusted status' by retrospectively adjusting earlier categorisations using the most up-to-date and best-informed evaluations (including current information and taxonomy), following the approach of Butchart et al. (2007). As in the assessment of the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species, when the conservation status of taxon changes in the NZTCS assessments, the reason for this change is recorded. Therefore, we can identify species that are genuinely improving or deteriorating in status (i.e. excluding changes due to taxonomic status or improved knowledge). Hence, the adjusted NZTCS status matches the status from the most-recent assessment (Figure 1A), except when a taxon has undergone a genuine improvement or deterioration in conservation status (Figure 1B). If an earlier assessment excluded a small subset of species within a taxonomic group, we also used the most-recent assessment to assign an earlier conservation status, essentially conservatively assuming that their status had not changed over this time (Figure 1C).

Red List Index calculation

The RLI should only be calculated for taxonomic groups which have its full set of species assessed multiple times, because if only a subset of species is assessed, the resulting RLI is likely to be biased (because the subsets are likely biased for example in conservation status, trends or distribution, Bubb et al. 2009). To derive a NZ national Red List Index (RLI), we included all taxonomic groups for which at least two comprehensive assessments of the risk of extinction each taxon is facing are available in the NZTCS (nztcs.org.nz). All included groups had at least two assessments of extinction risk for a very high proportion of, or all, species by December 2025 (Table 1). This way, the RLI trends presented here should be largely representative for the entire set of species in these group (Butchart et al 2025).

The RLI index ranges from 0 to 1, where a value of 1 equates to all species being categorised as Not Threatened (IUCN Least Concern), and hence that none are expected to go extinct in the near future, and a value of 0 indicates that all species have gone extinct (including possibly extinct, and extinct in the wild). Hence, decreasing RLI represents an increasing expected rate of species extinctions (and thus biodiversity loss), whereas an increase in RLI over time represents a decreasing expected future rate of species extinctions (thus a reduction in the rate of biodiversity loss). Unchanging RLI values indicate that the expected rate of extinctions for this species group remains the same (Bubb et al. 2009).

We used the established RLI equation (Butchart et al. 2007):

$$RLI_t = 1 - \sum S W_{c(t,s)} / (WEX * N), \quad (1)$$

where $W_{c(t,s)}$ is the weight for IUCN Category (c) at time (t) for species (s), WEX is the maximum weight (5, that is, the weight of (possibly) extinct species, see *RLI weights section* below), and N is the total number of assessed species, excluding those considered to be ‘Extinct’ in the year the set of species was first assessed (Butchart et al. 2007). Taxa that were ‘Taxonomically indistinct or ‘Not assessed’ in the most recent assessment were also excluded from the calculations. The calculation of the RLI is relevant to native resident taxa only because these are taxa being managed for conservation in Aotearoa. Consequently, we also excluded those species which were assessed as Introduced and Naturalised, or Non-resident Native in the most recent assessment (Rolfe et al. 2022).

There are various sources of uncertainty in estimating RLI trends, including (1) the treatment of data deficient species, (2) temporal variability (the ‘true’ RLI likely changes from year-to-year, but is only captured at multi-year intervals), and (3) uncertainty around linear interpolation between assessments (relevant for aggregated indices only). The uncertainty in the assignment of the categories at each assignment, is not yet able to be accurately represented, but we incorporated types 1-3 of uncertainties, following and building on Butchart et al. (2010), Juslén et al. (2016), Birdlife International (2020), and GeoBON (2022). We used a simulation approach for each taxonomic group, where during each run ($n = 1,000$) varying characteristics were assigned.

For each simulation run, the following characteristics were varied: (1) For each group, species were randomly sampled with replacement until the original number of species was attained (Juslén et al. 2016) and Data Deficient values were replaced by either (i) resampling from the empirical distribution of non-Data Deficient categories for the taxonomic group in the last assessment (Butchart et al. 2010) or (ii) if at least 10 taxa in the group had been previously been moved from Data Deficient to another classification status, we reweighted the empirical distribution based on the proportion of previously Data Deficient taxa that were assigned to a Threatened status. This second procedure was added recognising that, in particular for well-studied species groups (for example birds and reptiles), it is more likely that taxa in the Data Deficient category will ultimately be assigned a Threatened status. (2) An RLI for a given assessment year was assigned using a moving window of five years, centred on the focal year. (3) RLI values were calculated only for assessed years and these were then (a) fitted to a linear trend (for group-level RLI trend estimates), and (b) interpolated between years and extrapolated beyond the range using a slope, drawn from a normal distribution with a mean equal to the nearest observed slope and a coefficient of

variation of 60%, to account for extrapolation uncertainty (GeoBON, 2022) (used for aggregated RLI estimates, see below).

For each group, this resulted in a distribution of 1,000 RLI values per year, and one of slopes and intercepts. From this, we calculated the group-level mean RLI for each year and the mean rate of change over time, with 95% confidence intervals (CI, calculated as the 2.5 and 97.5 percentiles of the respective 1,000 sampling runs). Trends over time were considered statistically significant if the CI excluded zero (GeoBON, 2022). To calculate aggregated RLIs across groups (including ‘all included taxa’, ‘all included endemic taxa’, plants, and animal subgroups, see Table 1), we combined per-year RLI values using weighted means across groups (weights proportional to the number of species per group; Butchart et al. 2010, Bubb et al. 2009). We separately fitted a linear model to each of the 1,000 sampling runs across focal group species groups. As above, we calculated a mean and CI of the RLI trend (slopes) using the distribution of the slopes.

Red List Index weights

Using the increased granularity of the NZTCS, compared with the IUCN Red List categories, we assigned NZTCS weights to the conservation status and qualifiers (Table 2). This weighting acknowledges more granular improvement and differential extinction risk within one broad status, compared with the IUCN weighting. We provide results from supplementary analyses, including the national RLI based on the IUCN weights and using a dataset excluding the 818 putative taxonomic entities, in the Supplementary Information (Appendix 2).

NZTCS data are available on www.nztcs.org.nz. The analysis code is available upon reasonable request. All analyses were conducted in R (v. 5.1).

Figure 1. Genuine conservation status changes. An example of the effect of back-correcting of NZTCS categories, statuses and qualifiers, as used in the calculation of the RLI, using New Zealand bird taxa. Panel A) shows the number of bird taxa within each NZTCS status as reported in each NZTCS assessment since 2005. Any changes in conservation status between subsequent assessments represent a combination of updated taxonomy, updated or reinterpreted knowledge, and genuine changes in conservation status. Panel B) shows this same data but now back-corrected with most up-to-date information, hence including only genuine changes in NZTCS status, i.e. only showing changes for species with a genuine improvement or deterioration in the species' conservation status. Here, the most recent NZTCS status, which was determined using the most up-to-date taxonomy and knowledge was taken as the most accurate, and this was 'back-corrected' to previous assessments, and only adjusted to a different status if a genuine improvement or deterioration in the species' conservation status was reported in a NZTCS assessment. The differences between A and B then relates to all the changes due to updated taxonomy and knowledge. For calculation of the RLI, we then back-filled the status of any taxa that were not included in a previous assessment with their category/status as per the next assessment in which they were included (Panel C).

Table 1. Broad groupings and taxonomic subsets incorporated in the NZ national Red List Index (RLI) 2005-2025. Table indicates, per group, how many taxa were included in the RLI, and how many of those were classified as 'Data Deficient' in the most-recent assessment; the reason and number of taxa that were excluded (including those that were classified as 'Extinct' in the first assessment, and those taxa that are Introduced and Naturalised, or Non-residents), and the assessment years.

Broad group/domain	Taxonomic subset	RLI included		RLI excluded			Assessment year included																				
		Total	Data deficient	Extinct	Introduced/ Naturalised	Non-resident	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Plants+	Hornworts and liverworts	760	174	0	9	1																					
	Lichens	2026	1107	0	0	0																					
	Vascular plants	2805	115	6	2	33																					
Freshwater invertebrates	Freshwater insects	511	108	0	0	0																					
	Freshwater molluscs	79	39	0	0	0																					
	Other freshwater invertebrates	80	31	0	0	0																					
Freshwater vertebrates	Freshwater fish	53	0	1	21	3																					
Marine invertebrates	Corals & sea anemones	84	36	0	0	0																					
	Marine arthropods	186	68	0	0	0																					
	Marine molluscs	286	13	0	0	0																					
	Other marine invertebrates	230	141	0	0	0																					
Marine vertebrates	Marine mammals	40	21	0	0	17																					
	Chondrichthyans	108	51	0	0	5																					
Terrestrial invertebrates	Earthworms	177	105	0	2	0																					
	Orthoptera	157	17	0	5	0																					
	Powelliphanta	67	5	0	0	0																					
	Other gastropoda	156	21	0	0	0																					
	Spiders	1107	493	0	49	0																					
Terrestrial vertebrates	Amphibians	14	1	3	4	0																					
	Bats	5	1	0	0	1																					
	Birds	217	0	62	35	177																					
	Reptiles	149	13	1	1	8																					

Table 2. NZTCS Conservation statuses and qualifiers and ‘equivalent’ IUCN categories, with weights used in the calculation of the RLI.

RLI Weight as per IUCN, Butchart et al. 2007	IUCN Red List of Threatened Species Categories	NZTCS Conservation Statuses and Qualifiers post 2024 ²	NZTCS Conservation statuses and Qualifiers pre-2024	NZTCS RLI Weight
0	Least Concern	Not Threatened	Not Threatened	0
1	Near Threatened	At Risk – Recovering	At Risk – Recovering (criterion B) ⁴	0.5
		At Risk – Uncommon (natural state) ³	At Risk – Sparse ⁵ At Risk – Range Restricted ⁵ At Risk – Naturally Uncommon ⁶	0.5
		At Risk – Uncommon (unnatural state) ⁴	At Risk – Sparse ⁵ At Risk – Range Restricted ⁵ At Risk – Naturally Uncommon ⁶ At Risk – Relict ⁴	0.75
		At Risk – Declining	Chronically Threatened – Gradual Decline ⁵	1
2	Vulnerable	Threatened – Nationally Increasing	At Risk – Recovering (criterion A) ⁶	1.5
		Threatened – Nationally Vulnerable	Chronically Threatened – Serious Decline ⁵	2
3	Endangered	Threatened – Nationally Endangered	Threatened – Nationally Endangered	3
4	Critically Endangered	Threatened – Nationally Critical	Threatened – Nationally Critical	4
5 (WEX) ¹	Critically Endangered (Possibly Extinct), Critically Endangered (Possibly Extinct in the Wild), Extinct in the Wild, or Extinct.	Extinct Extinct in the Wild (EW) Possibly Extinct (PE)	Extinct Extinct in the Wild (EW) Possibly Extinct (PE)	5

¹ ‘Possibly Extinct’ and ‘Extinct in the Wild’ are qualifier-tags applied to species assessed in the NZTCS as Threatened – Nationally Critical (both qualifiers) or Data Deficient (qualifier ‘Possibly Extinct’ only).

² NZTCS conservation statuses and qualifiers defined in the manual of Rolfe et al. 2022 and used in assessments since 2024.

³ A population is considered ‘natural’ if its current size or area of occupancy is not the result of human-induced influences (Rolfe et al. 2022)

⁴ A population is considered ‘unnatural’ if its current size or area of occupancy is smaller than what it would have been in the absence of human-induced influences (Rolfe et al. 2022)

⁵ NZTCS conservation statuses and qualifiers only defined in the manual of Molloy et al. 2002 and used from 2002-2007.

⁶ NZTCS conservation statuses and qualifiers only defined in the manual of Townsend et al. 2008 and used from 2008-2024.

3. Results

Aggregated national RLI

We computed RLIs that are relevant to the New Zealand context for more than 20 taxonomic groups based on 9,297 taxa, including 6,094 endemic taxa and 2,560 data deficient taxa (Table 1). The aggregated NZ national RLI is relatively high (RLI in 2025 = 0.88, $n = 9,297$), meaning that relatively few taxa's national populations are close to extinction (Figure 3A). The index remained constant between 2005 and 2025 (non-significant slope = $-0.0001/\text{yr}$, CI -0.0007 to 0.0005), indicating that, overall, across the included taxa, there were no consistent changes in conservation status (Figure 2, Table A2.1). When assessing only endemic species ($n = 6,094$), the NZ national RLI was very similar and stable (RLI_{endemic} in 2025 = 0.87, non-significant slope = $-0.0002/\text{yr}$, CI -0.001 to 0.0007 ; Figure 2).

Calculating the RLI using the IUCN weights resulted in a slightly lower index (RLI_{IUCNWT} = 0.85 in 2025) than when based on NZTCS weights, and again, the data did not show a significant trend over time (Supplementary Information, Fig A2.1 and Table A2.1).

Figure 2. Aggregated NZ national Red List Index (NZ-RLI) for all 9,297 included and 6,094 endemic taxa. Dashed lines represent non-significant trends, while a solid line represents a significant trend over time. Shaded areas represent the 95 % confidence intervals (CI). Accompanying figure using IUCN weighting is included in the Supplementary information (Figure A2.1).

4. Discussion

Key findings

Capturing some 25% of existing biota (of the 37,000 identified native species listed in Costello 2024), the NZ national RLI, presented here may be one of the most comprehensive RLIs globally. It was calculated based on New Zealand Threat Classification System (NZTCS) assessments of those taxon groups that have the entire set of taxa included. With more than 23 groups incorporated, this index is more representative of the national extinction risk trend than the globally disaggregated RLI (which only includes mammals, birds, cycads and corals) (Butchart et al 2025). Its representativeness is supported by the strengths of the NZTCS process which adjusts criteria and categories to account for the archipelago's biogeography and, as per IUCN protocols, incorporates taxa with less certain estimates (data poor or low confidence level in estimating population size and trend) (Rolfe et al. 2022).

The NZ national aggregated RLI shows a stable trend around 0.88 meaning that relatively few species' national populations have moved closer to extinction in the past 20 years. Most New Zealand taxa have experienced historical decline following the settlement of human populations in the region, leading to 81 endemic taxa being extinct as per 2025 (Department of Conservation 2025). These extinctions were primarily caused by large-scale habitat modification, predation by introduced species and harvesting in the past 1,000 years (Duncan and Blackburn 2004, Duncan and Young 2000, Perry et al. 2014, Wilson 1997). Over this period, New Zealand indigenous forest has been reduced to 24% of its original extent and wetlands to 10% (Dymond et al. 2021, Ewers et al. 2006). Deforestation rate over the study period was very low (-0.001%) (Ewers et al. 2006) and species declines have slowed down or stabilised thanks to increased habitat protection and conservation efforts (Star 2002). This may explain the lack of significant trend in the New Zealand national aggregated RLI scores.

Tailored NZ National RLI and robustness

The tailored conservation status categories and qualifiers of the NZTCS allow a more granular assessment of the extinction risk. Using associated NZTCS-specific RLI weights provides greater differentiation among the At Risk subcategories by incorporating qualifiers. Hence, the NZTCS weights better capture ecological realities of endemic species with small populations or restricted ranges, which are typical in island ecosystems. Nonetheless, still aligns closely with IUCN weighting for threatened categories, ensuring comparability while reflecting national priorities. In fact, status and trend calculations of NZ national RLI using IUCN weights and NZTCS weights did not differ qualitatively at the aggregated level (Appendix 2).

The status and trend of the NZ national RLI based on almost 10,000 taxa differ from the globally disaggregated RLI for this country. Concomitant with the increase in representation (Bubb et al. 2009), the value of the NZ national RLI is much higher and stable, compared with the lower and declining globally disaggregated RLI for this country. The global RLI currently includes five comprehensively assessed taxonomic groups: mammals (5,801 species); birds (11,126 species); amphibians (6,771 species); cycads (307 species); and reef-forming corals (868 species) (IPBES 2019). The disaggregated global RLI for New Zealand provided by the IUCN comprises fewer than 300 taxa (48 species of mammals, 233 species of birds, 4 species of amphibians and 13 species of corals; note no cycads are native to New

Zealand; www.iucnredlist.org/assessment/red-list-index). This nationally disaggregated index shows a declining trend over a 30-year period (from 0.74 in 1993 to 0.62 in 2020), suggesting that New Zealand's contribution to global biodiversity loss is increasing. This is in contrast to the NZ national RLI presented here, which shows no change over the past two decades. Compared with the declining disaggregated global RLI, we propose that the stable trend of the NZ national RLI presented here, encompassing a 30-fold increase in comprehensiveness using a framework relevant to the country's biogeography, is more representative of the overall trend in conservation status of the biota of this archipelago over the last twenty years.

Limitations and hidden risks

Despite the increase in representativeness, the NZ national RLI still only captures a relatively small fraction of the country's biodiversity. While some groups (including all terrestrial and freshwater vertebrate taxonomic groups) are entirely captured, large groups of invertebrate biodiversity and other groups (including fungi and mosses) are not (yet). More generally, the RLI does not comprise an unknown and potentially large number of 'intractable' species, which continue to decline at variable rates (Hare et al. 2019).

As happens when aggregating data, the overall conservation status depicted by the national RLI does not represent the current risk of extinction of the individual taxa within it. Out of the 9,297 captured by the national RLI, 840 taxa are classed as Threatened (along with 2,359 as At Risk of becoming threatened, 3,531 as Not Threatened, and 2,567 as Data Deficient). As of 2025, 80 taxa incorporated in this study remain assessed in the NZTCS with forecasted rate of population decline of >70% over the longer of 10 years or three generations - maximum 100 years (and are thus listed as Nationally Critical, see Table A.2.2). An additional 1,702 taxa are known to have naturally small populations and are ultimately vulnerable to extreme natural or human-induced threats (nztc.org.nz, consulted on 23/12/2025). Aggregation at lower levels is likely to be more conservation relevant than aggregations at national-scale or broad domains. Taken together, to better assess and understand biodiversity loss, its drivers and its related consequences, extinction risk should be interpreted alongside other indicators of change such as population abundance, habitat extent and condition, and threats (Butchart et al. 2025).

In Aotearoa, long-term large scale predator control, which started in the 1930s, aims at reducing or eliminating introduced mammals such as rodents, possums and ungulates to stimulate habitat regeneration and biodiversity recovery (Leathwick and Byrom 2023). For example, a 3-year predator control operation cycle was estimated to result in a 2% annual population increase in the North Island brown kiwi (*Apteryx mantelli*), a species that has recovered from being Threatened – Nationally Vulnerable in 2008 to being Not Threatened in 2021 (Robertson et al. 2019, 2021). Although pest control is effective in suppressing targeted predators, only a few species appear to benefit from this management because of inter-specific competition, and biodiversity response being highly dependent on operational cycle length and timing (Robertson et al. 2019, Malham et al. 2023, Mortimer et al. 2025). Meso-predator release of mice (*Mus musculus*) is a significant issue of predator control for many taxa, particularly lizards which combine small body size and in Aotearoa very low fecundity and very long generation times. Kererū, New Zealand native wood pigeon (*Hemiphaga novaeseelandiae*), is one of the bird species known to benefit from large-scale predator control. It is assessed in the NZTCS as Not Threatened and qualified as being Conservation

Dependant, meaning it is likely to have a worse conservation status if the current management ceases (Ruffell and Didham 2017, Robertson et al 2021, Rolfe et al. 2022). Of all taxa assessed in the NZTCS as of December 2025, 550 taxa were qualified as Conservation Dependant (nztc.org.nz, 23/12/2025). Of these, 27 were in the Not Threatened category (i.e. with a RLI weight of 0), leading to an underrepresentation of their vulnerability.

Migratory taxa pose unique conservation challenges because they move across international borders and depend on large-scale, coordinated efforts (Williams et al. 2006, Martin et al. 2007, Nevins et al. 2009, Runge et al. 2014, Fraser et al. 2019, Schlesselmann et al. 2024). Many are vulnerable to threats such as bycatch, habitat loss, and climate change (UNEP-WCMC 2024). However, non-resident native taxa (classified as Migrant, Vagrant, or Coloniser in the NZTCS) were excluded from the NZ national RLI, yet at least 25 of these species are listed as threatened on the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species (Hitchmough et al. 2021, Robertson et al. 2021, Lundquist et al. 2025, Duffy et al. 2025). New Zealand participates in global agreements like the Convention on Migratory Species (CMS) to address these risks. However, migratory species remain outside the scope of the NZ national RLI, and in particular the RLI calculation for marine vertebrates does not represent the full range of species that use New Zealand waters and shores.

Future needs

To enhance the value of the NZ national RLI as a relevant biodiversity indicator, several priorities emerge. First, efforts to expand coverage to include currently underrepresented groups (particularly many invertebrate groups, fungi, and other poorly known taxon groups). Second, integrating migratory species and exploring methods to account for transboundary populations would strengthen alignment with international conservation obligations. Thirdly, assessments of the right level of aggregation are required to ensure that the index is ecologically sensible and relevant for conservation. These improvements will enable linking RLI status and/or trends to management activities and conservation investment (McCarthy et al. 2008), which ultimately could provide a powerful tool for evaluating the effectiveness of resource allocation and guiding optimal expenditure. As time-series data lengthen and taxonomic coverage broadens, the NZ national RLI and its disaggregated components, complemented with additional indicators such as population abundance, habitat extent and condition, and threat intensity, will become increasingly valuable for benchmarking progress and informing adaptive conservation strategies (Szabo et al. 2012).

5. Conclusion

We have successfully computed the first national Red List Index (RLI) for Aotearoa New Zealand, providing a benchmark that reflects the country's unique biogeography and conservation context. Our work highlights an opportunity for RLI frameworks to adopt similar practices to improve representativeness. The index's value lies in its ability to track genuine changes in extinction risk over time relevant to the country's context, and to highlight knowledge gaps (particularly fungi, and within the invertebrates). Although the NZ national RLI shows a stable trend over the last two decades, this does not imply that biodiversity loss in Aotearoa has halted, as individual taxa still suffer population declines within or across conservation status categories and 5-yearly assessments do not capture rapid

changes. The RLI should be interpreted alongside other indicators (e.g. population abundance, habitat extent and condition, and threat intensity). Future work should continue to expand taxonomic coverage of NZTCS and further explore disaggregation at ecologically meaningful scales, ensuring that this tool informs adaptive management and accelerates progress toward halting biodiversity loss.

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Appendix 1. Total number of taxa assessed in the NZTCS (2005-2025).

Table A1. Number of taxa assessed per year per taxonomic group, total number of estimated recognised taxa per group (# Taxa, this includes all species assessed, which can include extinct, introduced and non-resident taxa, but excludes taxonomically indistinct, not assessed, not listed taxa). If a taxonomic group was incorporated into the New Zealand national RLI, the column “RLI Taxa” indicates the number of taxa included (these only include native extant taxa, see Table 1 in main text). Years with taxa numbers in italics are not included in RLI calculations, due to only a (potentially biased) subset of the taxa in that group being included in the assessment (see main text).

To be provided

Appendix 2. Supplementary results from RLI calculation using different category weights

Figure A1.1. Aggregated NZ national Red List Index using NZTCS (A, replicate of Figure 3 in the main text) and IUCN weights (B) for endemic (red) and all incorporated taxa (black). See Table 2 in the main text for the different weights used.

Table A2.1. NZ national Red List Index from 2005-2025, based on NZTCS weights and included taxa at the level incorporated in the NZTCS (NZ-RLI), and for comparison, using IUCN weights (n = 9,297); and using taxonomically determinate taxa only (n = 8,479). Data represent the mean calculated based on included taxa per year (with 95% confidence interval in brackets) and are visualised in Figure A1.1.

Year	NZ-RLI (n = 9,297) NZTCS weights	Equivalent (n = 9,297) IUCN weights	Taxonomically determinate taxa only NZTCS weights (n = 8,479)
2005	0.8841 (0.8755-0.892)	0.8506 (0.8416-0.8588)	0.8970 (0.8886-0.9052)
2006	0.884 (0.8759-0.8914)	0.8505 (0.8422-0.8581)	0.8969 (0.8891-0.9045)
2007	0.8839 (0.8763-0.8907)	0.8504 (0.8428-0.8574)	0.8968 (0.8895-0.9039)
2008	0.8838 (0.8767-0.8901)	0.8502 (0.8431-0.8566)	0.8967 (0.8900-0.9032)
2009	0.8837 (0.8771-0.8896)	0.8501 (0.8435-0.8559)	0.8966 (0.8905-0.9024)
2010	0.8836 (0.8775-0.8892)	0.8500 (0.8439-0.8555)	0.8965 (0.8909-0.9018)
2011	0.8834 (0.8780-0.8888)	0.8499 (0.8442-0.8550)	0.8964 (0.8911-0.9012)
2012	0.8833 (0.8784-0.8883)	0.8498 (0.8446-0.8546)	0.8964 (0.8914-0.9008)
2013	0.8832 (0.8784-0.8878)	0.8497 (0.8448-0.8543)	0.8963 (0.8916-0.9005)
2014	0.8831 (0.8784-0.8875)	0.8495 (0.8449-0.8540)	0.8962 (0.8916-0.9002)
2015	0.8830 (0.8784-0.8873)	0.8494 (0.8449-0.8538)	0.8961 (0.8916-0.9001)
2016	0.8829 (0.8785-0.8873)	0.8493 (0.8449-0.8536)	0.8960 (0.8916-0.8999)
2017	0.8827 (0.8783-0.8870)	0.8492 (0.8447-0.8537)	0.8959 (0.8916-0.8999)
2018	0.8826 (0.8781-0.8870)	0.8491 (0.8442-0.8536)	0.8958 (0.8913-0.9001)
2019	0.8825 (0.8777-0.8872)	0.8490 (0.8439-0.8538)	0.8957 (0.8909-0.9002)
2020	0.8824 (0.8773-0.8874)	0.8488 (0.8433-0.8541)	0.8956 (0.8904-0.9004)
2021	0.8823 (0.8767-0.8877)	0.8487 (0.8428-0.8545)	0.8955 (0.8900-0.9007)
2022	0.8822 (0.8761-0.8879)	0.8486 (0.8419-0.8548)	0.8954 (0.8895-0.9012)
2023	0.8821 (0.8755-0.8881)	0.8485 (0.8413-0.8553)	0.8953 (0.8888-0.9018)
2024	0.8819 (0.8750-0.8885)	0.8484 (0.8407-0.8554)	0.8952 (0.8882-0.9022)
2025	0.8818 (0.8744-0.8889)	0.8482 (0.8401-0.8557)	0.8952 (0.8877-0.9026)